

The Uniqueness of Uḍḍiyāna-Tantra and Its Significance: A Brief Discussion

Dr Raktim Mukherjee

Uḍḍiyāna. The name itself is sufficient to evoke keen interest among the enthusiasts of Tantra. Uḍḍiyāna is revered as the foremost centre of Tantra during Pāla and Sena period. A number of Tibetan Buddhist texts including Bstan-hgyur and descriptions of Lāmā Tāranath mention Uḍḍiyāna as the birthplace of Vajrayāna.

The core philosophical idea of assimilating Prajñā and Mahākaruṇa with Śūnyatā took a much simpler form in the sect of Vajrayāna through manifestations of deities and their maṇḍalas. This helped the larger masses to access what was rather a restricted ambience in the Mahayāna school of philosophy. And if Uḍḍiyāna is the starting point of all these; then certainly its importance is unfathomable for the historical trajectory of tantra.

Bringing revolution on the ground, and uplifting a shattered nation to a glorious height; this Vajrayāna sect of Tantra served as the life-giver to Pāla era, all thanks to Uḍḍiyāna. The aforementioned Tibetan sources further indicate that when Vajrayāna sect started to crumble due to top-heaviness, and became complicated at the end of 10th century AD; it's Uḍḍiyāna which again served as the birthplace of a radical revolutionary movement; the Sahajayāna. Siddha Naropā, Nigumā and the famous 84 mahāsiddhas started their glorious tradition of Sahaja movement from this mystical site of Tantra; the Uḍḍiyāna pītha.

This indicates that with progressing time, instead of turning into a stagnant and senile institute of knowledge; Uḍḍiyāna served as an ever-refreshing source of knowledge and compassion, which enriched the ancient society of Greater Bengal and its surrounding areas of influence.

As per Tantric texts; Uḍḍiyāna is revered as one of the 4 Ādi Pīthas, the 4 primordial shrines built upon the bodily remain of mythical divine mother Satī; the other three being Jālandhara, Kāmarūpa, Pūrṇagiri.

But surprisingly, even after ages of research, we still don't know the exact location of Uḍḍiyāna. Many scholars have tried to identify it with numerous ancient sites; from Jagannātha Kṣetra of Puri, Odisha to the village Vajrayoginī of Bangladesh, the birthplace of Atīśa. Some identified it with Shangri-la, whereas some opined it to be located at Odantapurī of Magadha, nowadays near Bihar Sharif. And unfortunately, while Tantra scholars remained busy in this everlasting debate, another much more

important matter remained elusive and far from any discussion, i.e. the spectacularly unique tantric rites and rituals of Uḍḍiyāna.

In Sādhanamālā, Guhya-Samāja-Tantra and other texts, while describing sādhanas of numerous deities, textual authors have often mentioned many a sādhanas belonging to Uḍḍiyāna. These sādhanas are mentioned as "Uḍḍiyāna-krama", "Uḍḍiyāna-binirgata"(emerging from Uḍḍiyāna), "Uḍḍiyāna-pithāntargata" (under the school of Uḍḍiyāna shrine), Uḍḍiyāna-tantrokta (mentioned in Uḍḍiyāna tantra) etc.

The noteworthy point is that regardless of the deity worshipped in those kramas, the wrathful evil-banishing fierce form of that deity has been revered. In this matter; sādhana of Vajravārāhī, Mārīcī, Kurukullā, Nairātmā, Āryatārā, Jāngulī etc bear striking similarities. Each of these sādhanas demand separate and thorough discussions. But even if we try to compile them in a nutshell; some unique features surely come out. And that is; whichever form of these māṭṛkās might have been worshipped otherwise; at Uḍḍiyāna, all of them are engaged in fierce battle, dancing magnificently, avenging the perils of the universe. Wrathful smile is making their face gorgeous, yet awe-inspiring, and all of them are decorated with garlands of severed heads and wearing tiger skins.

Aside pleasant and compassionate forms, worshipping mother goddesses in such awe-inspiring forms bear a profound significance. One cannot go deep into the root of a tradition without securing the entrance to that tradition. We can understand this with a few examples. The goddess Nairātmā is considered in Tantra as the mother of purest knowledge or Prajñā and giver of Kaivalya or liberation from this endless cycle of life and death. She is the chief yoginī (yoginīmukhya) and the manifestation of nirātmā, the stage where the separation between self and others goes away. Caryāpadas are sung mentioning her as the merciful Dombī or mysterious Śabarī, who does not reveal herself to Tīrthikas and Vedic Brahmins. In Uḍḍiyāna krama; we see her wrathful form, wearing the garland of severed heads and dancing upon the cosmic lotus.

Thus, the essence of liberation and purest knowledge have been manifested here by the wrathful mother goddess. Similar ideas can be found in the maṇḍala of Tvaritā; the "Nityā " or the snake goddess mentioned in Tantrarāja. Tvaritā herself is very merciful, with loving smile in her face, sitting in Lalitāsana. But her associate Sphetara is fierce, protecting the entrance to Tvaritā with vajra, bows and arrows. This clearly indicates towards a common theme of the Tantra of Pāla era; fierce and wrathful outside and compassionate inside. From numerous other examples of this theme, e.g. that of Āryatārā, Marīcī, Jāngulī; we can see that this unique feature was a contribution of Uḍḍiyāna in the Tantric tradition of ancient Bengal.

Another very important feature is revealed if we go through the iconography of these māṭṛkās as described in Uḍḍiyāna. That is, the emergence of iconography of Kālī, the most popular mother goddess

of tantra and certainly Bengal, continuing from Pāla era to nowadays. All those descriptions of wrathful mātṛkās; with garlands of severed heads, wearing tiger skins, surrounded by Piśācas, Yoginīs, Vetālas etc, dancing on corpses in the cremation ground indicate the grand emergence of Kālī to the central tenet of tantra in the present form. This process started in the 10th century AD, progressing rapidly in the next centuries with the advent of Sahajayāna, that made the core concept of Tantra accessible to everyone.

In support of this inference, we can consider archaeological evidence of numerous icons of Kālī found since this time throughout the Indian subcontinent; from North to South. At this time, a lot of mātṛkās gained popularity in Bengal and its surroundings, like Carcikā, Vajradākinī, Parṇaśavarī, Kurukullā who have striking similarities with Kālī, not only in iconography but also in rites and rituals. Kurukullā was, at this time, gradually progressing to become assimilated within Kālī's maṇḍala of 15 nityās, who are worshipped even today everywhere during Kālī Pūjā.

In the maṇḍalas of Mahākāla and other male deities, Kālī is not only a part and parcel; but these maṇḍalas indicate that Kālī was being considered the same as the male deity worshipped in the centre of the maṇḍalas. The supreme goddess of Tantra emerged out of the unique rites of Uḍḍiyāna.

Another important point regarding uniqueness of Uḍḍiyāna is that most of the sādhanas mentioned under this school describe the mother goddess as Kumārī i.e. without any consort. Āryatārā and ĀryaJāngulī are two typical examples of this non-dual principle. Besides, we can see that the dhyanas of Uḍḍiyāna-Kurukullā and Uḍḍiyāna-binirgatā-Māricī make no mention regarding their kulas (usually identified as the Tathāgata residing atop their crown). It indicates that Uḍḍiyāna had, to some extent, surpassed the boundaries of typical Vajrayāna theology, and started to confer on the mother goddess her original glorious form. As a result of this revolutionary idea, we can see that Āryatārā, who was narrated as being born from the tears of Avalokitesvara in Vajrayāna, has gradually become unified with other cults of mother goddess to construct a vast cult of mātṛkā by the Sena era. To support this inference, we can look into the Tārā stotra of Sadukti-Karṇāmṛta where Āryatārā is viewed as Gaurī, Girijā, Kuśalā, Mangalā, Padmāvati (the snake goddess Manasā or Jāngulī) and Gāyatrī. Surpassing the boundaries of particular yānas or sects, this magnificent renaissance of mother goddess cult was the cornerstone for future Tantras. Future was beginning to take form at Uḍḍiyāna.

We know that, as per the original version of Sāṃkhya school of philosophy, which also happens to be a cornerstone of the earliest philosophy of Tantra, the one and only Prakṛti is omnipotent, root of creation and destruction. But in later periods, with gradual progression of patriarchal views of society and religion corrupted this early philosophy and created a perverted dualist version of Sāṃkhya and Tantra; as explained by Dr Narendra Nath Bhattacharya.

We can say that these perverted versions were demolished to bring forth the original structure of mother goddess cult by this unique approach of Uḍḍiyāna Tantra at the uprising period of Sahajayāna. The repeated mentioning of "Kumārī" (without consort) form of māṭṛkā is clearly suggestive of this monism. We can get a more lucid idea if we study the evolution of the snake goddess cult in this regard.

Since Gupta era to the period of Mātsyanyāya, we find that the primitive snake goddess cult was gradually being assimilated within patriarchal Śaiva mythology. Narratives were being created regarding her lineage, family etc. Mahabharata mentioned that she was the sister of Vāsukī Nāga, wife of Jaratkāru, the angry penancing saint who abandoned her for no reason, and mother of saint Āstika. Later Tantras described her as an illegitimate child of Śiva, who faced the wrath of Goddess Candikā. In Yoginītantra, the serpent goddess's cult has been described as a mean of filthy abhicārās to kill or mute or destroy enemies.

We can find similar narratives regarding her cult as an evil power in the period of Mātsyanyāya by the legends told by Lāmā Tāranath. Thus, once worshipped in the early Bengali civilisations of Gangaridai as pleasant, merciful, compassionate goddess residing in lotus garden; the snake goddess cult was severely vilified over a period of time. But then comes the path breaking approach of Uḍḍiyāna; revealing the fierce Kumārī form of ĀryaJāngulī; which depicts wrath over evil forces and compassion for the suffering world at the same time. ĀryaJāngulī is described as dancing over the hoods of seven nāgas, her face adorable with coincident smile and wrath. She is wearing the garland of Gunja (a flower usually found in hills having high medicinal value).

She holds in her hand vajra, sword, bow and arrows, tarjanī mudrā and Viṣapustaka (a book describing the nature and management of different kinds of poisons). She is at times a wise healer, a loving mother for the suffering souls, and at other times a vengeful goddess for the evils of the world. With this theological innovation, since this period of Pāla era up to the late medieval periods, there was a humongous and enriched tradition of snake goddess cults; worshipped by Bengali society; which helps us understand the importance of the narratives put forward in Uḍḍiyāna.

Māṭṛkās in Uḍḍiyāna-krama were often depicted as the manifestation of Prajñā and Karuṇa. Poets of Caryāpadas described the cosmic dance of Nairātmā as:

এক সো পদুম চৌষট্টি পাখুরি

তহিঁ চড়ি নাচঅ ডোম্বী বাপুড়ী

(there is a single lotus, with 64 petals; upon which dances the mysterious Dombī).

Then, the Sahaja sect was established as the easiest way to reach her, who is otherwise unavailable for the Vedics and Tīrthikas:

নগর বাহিরে ডোম্বী তোহারি কুড়িয়া

ছুই ছুই যাওত ব্রাহ্মণ নাড়িয়া

(Oh Dombī! You reside outside the town. The Brahmins and Theravadis try to touch you but in vain.)

When she manifests herself as a Sabari (hunter woman of hilly areas); wearing garland of Gunjā flower; the poet sings:

উঁচা উঁচা পাবত তহি বসই শবরী বালি

মোরঙ্গ পিচ্ছ পরহিগ শবরী গিবত গুঞ্জরীমালী

(High hills are everywhere. There resides the Sabari. Her is ornamented with peacock tail. She wears garland of Gunjā flower.)

Such sweetness of poetry was revealed in Uḍḍiyāna in the tradition of mahāsiddhas; who shaped Tantra in the form of Sahaja to uplift the thoughtfulness of the greater masses. They did all these under the protection of wrathful and yet compassionate cult of Sahaja which was a beautiful revolutionary culture. When we see the famous Vaiṣṇava poets Vidyāpati and Candīdās worshipping goddess Cāmuṇḍā and Bāsuli; Nityānanda abadhūta, the famous leader of Gauḍīya Vaiṣṇava movement bearing an idol of goddess Aparajitā in his crown; we understand how a prolonged tradition to protect and redefine tantric culture was extending since the Pāla era in spite of the anarchy of medieval Bengal; and this tradition started its glorious journey in Uḍḍiyāna. This tradition gifted us with Caryāpadas and enriched the literature of renowned siddhas like Naropā, Nigumā, Saraha, Maitripā.

It is this tradition which took the prime structure of Vaishnavism in the famous Gītagovinda of Jayadeva; the court poet of Lakṣmaṇasena. This tradition has determined the future way of tantra; constructed the present iconography of Kālī and established the māṭrkās both the benevolent mother and fierce protector of this land. Therefore, the importance of Uḍḍiyāna, the mysterious site of Tantra in ancient Bengal casts an enduring legacy on the development of the cultural roots of Bengal.

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Dr Raktim Mukherjee holds an MBBS degree from Calcutta Medical College and is currently completing his MD. He has authored a number of books and articles in Bengali on the history of Tantra and Goddess cults. Proficient in Sanskrit and an independent researcher on Tantra, Dr Mukherjee is also a practitioner and devotee of Śākta religion.

